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PRACTICE OF BREAST SELF-EXAMINATION AMONG ANTENATAL ATTENDEES AT THE UNIVERSITY OF UYO TEACHING HOSPITAL, UYO, NIGERIA.

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Abstract:

Background: Breast self-examination is the most commonly available screening method for the detection of breast cancer. This is especially true in resource-poor settings due to its convenience, safety, and privacy. It also does not require the use of equipment or a visit to the hospital, which may not be readily accessible.

This study examines the awareness of breast cancer in antenatal attendees in our hospital and explores the knowledge, attitude, and practice of self-examination of the breast.

Methods: This was a cross-sectional study carried out over a 3-month period with the assistance of self-administered questionnaires administered to 115 consenting antenatal attendees at the University of Uyo Teaching Hospital.

Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 26. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the study data. Pearson's rank correlation was used to assess the relationship between continuous variables, and the Chi-square (χ^2) test was used to determine associations between categorical variables. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results: The mean age of the participants was 29.95 years. Almost 95% of patients (94.8%) had heard of breast cancer, although 33.9% did not think it was curable. Most (84.3%) patients recognized a breast mass as a symptom of breast cancer. Only 67.8% had ever performed a breast self-examination, and 22.6% knew when to do so appropriately. Almost 22% (21.7%) of the patients did not think that breast self-examination was useful.

The association between marital status and education level and the practice of breast self-examination was significant ($p < 0.001$)

Conclusion: Awareness of breast cancer was relatively high, but knowledge about breast self-examination was low. There was also a significant association between marital status and education level and the practice of breast self-examination. Greater enlightenment about the benefits of breast self-examination is needed. This is especially important in our environment, where health care awareness is low. This can be done by health care workers, including community workers, through mass media and home visits as well as during antenatal visits.

Keywords: Self-examination of the breast, Breast cancer, breast mass, antenatal attendees

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Introduction

Breast cancer is the most common mucocutaneous cancer among females worldwide.¹ In Africa, cancer was the most frequently reported cancer in 2020 (74.3/100,000 cases).²

Approximately 6.6% of all breast cancer cases are diagnosed in women aged 40 years or less.³ In Nigeria, the incidence of breast cancer is increasing, with 22.7% of cancer cases being that of the breast as of 2020.⁴ It has also been found that Nigeria has the lowest 3-year survival rates among the six countries studied, with Nigeria at 36%, Uganda at 44%, and South Africa at 56%.⁴

This low survival rate in African countries compared with that in the West is due to several reasons. Young people make up a large proportion of the population in Africa, and the incidence of breast cancer at a younger age is becoming more prevalent.⁵ Also, breast cancer in young females is more likely to be an aggressive subtype. Affected women are also more likely to present in the advanced stage of the disease because it is not only more aggressive but also has a low index of suspicion and lacks screening programs.^{6,7,8}

Pregnancy breast cancer accounts for 2-3% of all breast cancer cases.⁹ The increased vascularity and lymphatic drainage from the breast potentiates the metastatic spread of the cancer. However, the increased density of the breast during pregnancy makes it difficult to detect breast cancer early, even with screening methods.¹⁰

These screening methods include gene determination to assess susceptibility, clinical breast examination, breast self-examination, and mammography. The most common method by which breast cancer is detected is self-examination.¹¹

Since 1978, breast self-examination has been recognized as an effective method to diagnose breast cancer.^{12, 13.} Studies have shown that regular breast self-examination as well as breast awareness leads to earlier diagnosis of breast cancer, especially in low- and middle income countries where opportunities for clinical breast examination and mammography may be scarce or nonexistent.³ This is so despite the controversies involving the effectiveness of self-examination in reducing mortality and morbidity from breast cancer.^{12, 13, 14.}

Breast self-examination is safe, easy, and convenient and does not require any equipment.^{15, 16.} It also improves breast health awareness and is important in resource-poor countries, such as Nigeria.¹⁷

Breast self-examination involves using the tips and pads of the fingers to examine the breast while standing, sitting, or lying down. Its frequency is divided into the following three categories:

Infrequent breast self-examination, which is not done at all, is done once a year or 3-4 times a year.

Appropriate breast self-examination, which is performed monthly or fortnightly.

Excessive self-examination of the breast, which is done daily or more than once a day or weekly.

This study was conducted to determine the awareness, attitude, and knowledge of our pregnant women about self-examination. To the best of our knowledge, it is the first such study in our center. It is hoped that this study will increase the awareness of the need for breast self-examination, especially among pregnant women. It is hoped that this increased awareness will also translate into better breast health between pregnancies.

Methodology

This cross-sectional study was conducted at the University of Uyo Teaching Hospital, Uyo, Akwa-Ibom state, Nigeria.

The University of Uyo Teaching Hospital is a 500-bed tertiary hospital occupying approximately 43 hectares of land and currently serves a population of over 5 million people from Akwa Ibom and its neighboring states.

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The hospital was established in 1996 as Akwa Ibom State Specialist Hospital. In 2006, the institution was upgraded to a University Teaching Hospital to serve the then newly established College of Health Sciences, University of Uyo. Uyo is the capital of Akwa Ibom State and is located within the equatorial rainforest belt.

This study examined the awareness and knowledge of breast self-examination among patients attending our antenatal clinic. Out of the 141 eligible patients, 115 women aged 18 years and older were selected consecutively by convenience sampling and interviewed over a two-month period from March 1st to April 30th 2025.

The exclusion criteria included refusal to participate in the study, very ill patients, and those with a history of breast cancer.

Approval was obtained from the research ethics committee of the institution, and informed consent was obtained from all the respondents.

Information was obtained using a pretested structured questionnaire. Information obtained included socio-demographic factors for example age, marital status, occupation, level of education, and number of children; awareness of breast cancer and its symptoms; and knowledge of breast self-examination and personal breast history. A referral to the general surgeon was obtained if any breast pathology was detected or reported.

The collected data were entered into the SPSS version 26 software. Descriptive statistics, such as means and proportions, were used to analyze the data. The relationship between breast self-examination practice and sociodemographic variables was assessed using Pearson’s chi-square test. The significance level was set at $p < 0.01$.

Results

Out of the 141 women selected, 115 were interviewed in the antenatal clinic of the University of Uyo Teaching Hospital, Uyo. (Response rate: 81.6%).

Table 1 shows the respondents’ sociodemographic factors. The majority of the women (39, (33.9%) were in the 26-30 years age group and most were married -107(93.02%). The respondents had mostly tertiary education (79 [68.7%]) and were mostly business people (52 [45.2%]). Of the respondents, 47 (40.9%) had no children.

Table 1: Respondents’ socio-demographic characteristics.

Variable	Category	N	%
Age (years)	20–25	23	20.0
	26–30	39	33.9
	31–35	34	29.6
	>35	19	16.5
	Total	115	100.0
Marital Status	Married	107	93.0
	Single	6	5.2
	Divorced/Widowed	2	1.7
	Total	115	100.0

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Variable	Category	N	%
Level of education	Primary	4	3.5
	Secondary	32	27.8
	Tertiary	79	68.7
	Total	115	100.0
Occupation	Student	19	16.5
	Teacher	22	19.1
	Business	52	45.2
	Farmer	3	2.6
	Civil Servant	13	11.3
	Youth Corper	3	2.6
	Others	3	2.6
	Total	115	100.0
Number of children	0	47	40.9
	1	38	33.0
	2	18	15.7
	3	11	9.6
	≥4	1	0.9
	Total	115	100.0

Table 2 reveals the degree of awareness of the respondents about breast cancer and their knowledge of breast cancer symptoms. A total of 109 respondents had heard of breast cancer (94.8), but 39 (33.9%) did not think it was curable. Most (97, (84.3%) recognized a breast lump as a symptom of breast cancer, and most agreed that pain (90, (78.3%), redness 84 (73.0%), nipple discharge (76, (66.1%), and nipple retraction (57.4%) were symptoms of breast cancer.

Table 2. Awareness of Breast Cancer among Respondents

Question	Response	N	%
Have you heard of breast cancer?	No	6	5.2
	Yes	109	94.8
	Total	115	100.0
Is breast cancer curable?	No	39	33.9

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Question	Response	N	%
	Yes	76	66.1
	Total	115	100.0

: Knowledge of Respondents of Breast Cancer Symptoms

Question	Response	N	%
Is nipple discharge a symptom of breast cancer?	No	39	33.9
	Yes	76	66.1
	Total	115	100.0
Is nipple retraction a symptom of breast cancer?	No	49	42.6
	Yes	66	57.4
	Total	115	100.0
Is breast pain a symptom of breast cancer?	No	25	21.7
	Yes	90	78.3
	Total	115	100.0
Is breast mass a symptom of breast cancer?	No	18	15.7
	Yes	97	84.3
	Total	115	100.0
Is breast redness a symptom of breast cancer?	No	31	27.0
	Yes	84	73.0
	Total	115	100.0

Table 3 shows a general overview of the practice of self-examination of the breast. Only 78 participants (67.8%) had ever undergone a breast self-examination as against 32.2% who had never undergone breast self-examination. Of the 78 patients who had undergone breast self-examination, only 26 (22.6%) did so correctly, which was monthly. Twelve patients (10.4%) had done so only once and an equal number 12 (10.4%) had done so yearly. Twenty-eight (24.3%) did so weekly. Ninety, 90 (78.3%) of the respondents reported that breast self-examination was useful, while 25 (21.7%) reported that it was not.

Table 3: Breast Self-Examination Practices among Respondents

Question	Response	N	%
Have you ever performed breast self-examination?	No	37	32.2
	Yes	78	67.8

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Question	Response	N	%
	Total	115	100.0
If yes, how often?	Never	37	32.2
	Once	12	10.4
	Yearly	12	10.4
	Monthly	26	22.6
	Weekly	28	24.3
	Total	115	100.0
Is self-examination of the breast useful?	No	25	21.7
	Yes	90	78.3
	Total	115	100.0

Discussion

Our study shows that most of our patients were in the 26-30 years bracket, were married, and had a tertiary education.

The majority of the respondents knew about breast cancer, but many did not think that it was curable. Most agreed that palpating a breast mass, as well as pain, redness, nipple discharge, and nipple retraction, is a likely symptom of breast cancer. Most of the respondents had also heard about breast self-examination, but only a few knew how to perform it correctly.

The high level of awareness of breast cancer among our women is encouraging. This is because a high awareness of breast cancer leads to better health-seeking behaviors.¹⁸ Furthermore, knowledge of the early warning signs of breast cancer was high. This is in contrast to an earlier study in Angola, which found a low level of knowledge of the early warning signs of breast cancer.¹⁹

In this study, the prevalence of breast self-examination was 67.8%. This is higher than that found in other studies. In Enugu, Nigeria, the prevalence of breast self-examination was found to be 62%.²⁰ Other studies have also reported high prevalence rates.^{21, 22, and 23}

This high prevalence of breast self-examination is important and reflects an increased awareness of breast health, which can help in the early detection of breast cancer. Breast self-examination remains the most common method of discovering breast cancer in women, especially in low- and middle-income countries where mammography and clinical breast examination require expensive equipment and a visit to a health care facility¹³. This equipment is not readily available in this region of the world, and hospital visits are cumbersome because they require a small amount of money, particularly in rural areas where the majority of the population reside. Breast self-examination becomes even more necessary during pregnancy because of the increased incidence of breast cancer

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in pregnancy and a delay in diagnosis^{9,10}. This high prevalence of breast self-examination in our studies may be because most of our patients were highly educated.

A high literacy level correlates with increased levels of knowledge and health behavior among respondents^{24,25}. A high literacy level was also found in a study by Mahmoud et al. in Abuja, Nigeria,²⁶ In another study in Ibadan, also in Nigeria, educational attainment was associated with increased levels of practice of breast self-examination²²

Again, education appears to increase knowledge of breast cancer. Women residing in rural communities in Nigeria, where education is lacking, were found to have insufficient knowledge of breast cancer²³.

The majority of our patients were married, which is not surprising considering that the study was conducted among antenatal patients, most of whom are married and in a stable relationship. The level of awareness of breast cancer was high in this study (94.8%), and the majority of the respondents recognized the presence of a breast lump and other symptoms as suggestive of breast cancer.

Only 22.6% of our patients who had ever undergone breast self-examination did so correctly. This agrees with other studies. Kayode FO et al in Ilorin, Nigeria²¹, Okobia et al²³ and Mbanaso, et al²⁴ in Abia state, Nigeria, found a similar rate of low knowledge of the appropriate time to perform a breast self-examination. In another similar study in Ibadan, most respondents stated that a self-examination of the breast could be done at 'anytime'.²⁷

Breast self-examination is most appropriately performed monthly, between days 7 and 10 of the menstrual cycle.⁵ This allows for the subsidence of the swelling and tenderness of the breast that may occur before and during menstruation and creates a routine that the patient can more easily remember. Postmenopausal women are encouraged to choose a specific monthly date to perform a breast self-examination.

Marital status and level of education were found to be significantly associated with self-examination of the breast. Inadequate knowledge leads to poor awareness and practice of self-examination of the breast. This has also been found to be the case in other studies²⁷. Indeed, educational interventions improved self-examination practices of the breast.²⁸

In conclusion, the awareness of breast cancer in this study was high, even though the sample size was small and the study was hospital based. However, the appropriate period for breast self-examination, which is between days 7-10 of the menstrual cycle and method of breast self-examination were poorly known. Therefore, it is important for our women, not only our antenatal patients, to be taught by healthcare workers the proper method and timing of breast self-examination and the need to seek orthodox care if an abnormality is discovered. This can be done by trained healthcare workers, including midwives and community health workers, using pictures for demonstration. This may help in the earlier diagnosis of BC.

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